

Original Research Article

Assessment of the Practice of Ocular Self-Medication among Staff of College of Health Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi, North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

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Ocular self-medication practices among academic and non-academic staff of the College of Health Sciences, Benue State University and factors that led to ocular self-medication were accessed. A population based survey involving 146 respondents was conducted. Respondents were interviewed with the aid of a structured questionnaire composed of closed and open ended questions to collect data on demographics and ocular symptoms and self-medication practices. Descriptive statistical analysis was performed on the data to generate frequency distribution and percentages. Prevalence of ocular self-medication was 73.96% with painful red eye (40%) being the most common indication for which self-medication was practiced. Among the various drugs used, antibiotic was the commonest eye medication in 81(75%) respondents followed by steroids 17(15.74%). Main factors influencing self-medication were experience from previous ocular episode, the perception that the symptoms were a minor/simple disorder and warranted no expert care, advice from friends/relatives and long waiting time to access health care. Local patent medicine stores were the main source of drug for ocular self-medication. It is concluded that the practice of ocular self-medication is common among the population interviewed. Adequate health education of the public on the dangers of self diagnosis and treatment, possibly leading to the problem of drug resistance when appropriate indication of the medication is needed should be emphasised.

Keywords: Ocular symptoms, self-medication, tertiary institution, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Self-medication according to the World Health Organisation (WHO) definition, is the use of drugs to treat self-perceived diagnosed disorder or symptoms. This includes continued use of a prescribed drug for chronic or recurrent diseases or symptoms (WHO/DAP, 1993).

Self-medication is also defined as obtaining and consuming one or more drugs without the advice of a physician either for diagnosis, prescription or surveillance of the treatment (Montastruc et al., 1997). Self-

medication is practiced worldwide and has been reported to be very common in developing countries (Shankar et. Al.,2002). A major deficit of self-medication is the lack of clinical assessment of the health situation by an accredited traditional leader or medical professional which could result in misdiagnosis and delay in appropriate treatment (Kyei et al., 2014). Indiscriminate practice of self-medication results in wastage of resources, increases resistance of pathogens and

generally entails serious health hazards such as adverse reaction and prolonged suffering (Sonam et al., 2011). Blindness could also result from inappropriate use of drugs in self-medication for what may even seem like a minor eye condition.

One of the obstacles to reducing avoidable blindness is the limited access to appropriate eye care services (Paulo and Zanini, 1988). Other barriers compounding this inaccessibility are ignorance, cost, fear of care givers and transportation challenges. People who live in communities with inaccessible eye facilities tend to seek other alternative eye care services (Loyola et al., 2004). Reports indicated that less than 10% of people in low income countries receive optimal eye care mainly due to limited access to appropriate eye care services (Arrais et al., 1997).

Prevalence of ocular self-medication in different population groups have been studied. Kagashe and Msela (2012) reported that 59.8% of patients seen in ophthalmic clinics in Tanzania practised self-medication. In Ghana, Kyei et al. (2014) reported a 23.3% rate of ocular self-medication among respondents. Omalase et al. (2008) and Ajayi et al. (2014) reported a prevalence rate of 79% and 73.6% respectively in hospital based studies in South West Nigeria.

In North Central Nigeria, there is dearth of information regarding the practice of ocular self-medication. This study therefore, wanted to assess the prevalence and determinants of ocular self-medication practices among workers of a tertiary institution in Makurdi, North Central Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This study was a population based survey, and was conducted in the College of Health Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi in North Central Nigeria.

Data Collection Technique

The study was a descriptive cross-sectional study using a structured questionnaire composed of closed and open ended questions which were administered to a total of 146 workers comprising of academic and non-academic staff of the College of Health Sciences of the Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section contained questions regarding demographic characteristics consisting of age, gender, highest level of education and occupation. The second section of the questionnaire consisted of questions related to the attitudes towards eye care services and the practice of self-medication.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed on the data. This involved the use of statistical tools to generate frequency distribution and percentages (SAS, 2003).

RESULTS

A total of 146 workers were interviewed and 108(73.97%) admitted to have used self-eye-medication. Demographic characteristics of respondents are shown in Table 1 and revealed that 68(62.9%) were males and 40 (37.03%) were females. The male to female ratio was 1.7:1. Majority of the respondents (61.11%) were young adults (20 – 40 years) and the rest were under 20 years of age and old adults within the age range of 41 – 60 years respectively.

Seventy (46.8%) of the respondents were non-academic staff while thirty-eight (35.18%) were academic staff. The educational background of the respondents showed that majority (58%) had tertiary education (Polytechnic and University) followed by 46.0% with secondary school education and 4.0% had primary education.

Ocular symptoms for which self-medication was practised are shown in Table 2. Painful red eye 32(40.0%) was the most common indication followed by itching in the eye 21(26.0%), gradual visual loss 10(12.25%) and discharges 8(10.0%). Other symptoms include inability to read small print 6(7.5%), injuries 2(2.5%) and sudden visual loss 1 (1.25%). Analyses done to determine the most frequently ocular medication indicated the utilisation of antibiotics by 75% of those who practice self-medication (Table 3). Other drugs that were commonly used for the practice included steroids, anti allergy, traditional remedies and anti glaucoma, consisting 15.74%, 4.62%, 3.70% and 0.92% respectively.

Among the reasons for which self-medication was practised as shown in Table 4 are: 60(55.56%) was experience from previous illness, 20(18.51%) was due to the perception that the disease was simple or minor, 14(12.96%) was due to advice from family members or friends, 7(6.48%) was because of longer waiting at healthcare facility, 5(4.62%) was due to high cost of treatment at health facility and 2 (1.85%) was due to other reason like too busy or no reason.

This study had also assessed the kind of sources of medicine for self-eye medication by the respondents (Table 5). The findings indicated that the source was drug retail outlets (patent medicine stores) in the majority 66.0% of the cases. Other sources include visiting outreach programmes 11.1%, pharmacist, 9.20%, non doctor eye care worker, 7.40% and drug peddler and vendors, 5.50%.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Category/Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender/Sex		
Male	68	62.9
Female	40	37.03
Educational Status		
Primary	4	3.70
Secondary	46	42.59
Tertiary	58	53.70
Age (years)		
<20	22	20.37
21 – 40	66	61.11
41 – 60	20	18.51
Cadre of staff		
Academic	38	35.18
Non-Academic	70	46.8

Table 2. Indications for using self eye medications

Indications	Frequency	Percentages
Painful red eye	32	40%
Itching	21	26%
Discharges	8	10.0%
Gradual visual loss	10	12.25%
Sudden visual loss	1	1.25%
Inability to read small print	6	7.5%
Injuries	2	2.5%
Total	80	100%

Table 3. Type of Ocular Medication used.

Eye Medication	Frequency	Percentage
Antibiotic	81	75
Steroid	17	15.74
Anti allergy	5	4.62
TEM (Traditional Eye Medication)	4	3.70
Anti glaucoma	1	0.92
Total	108	99.98

Table 4. Factors influencing self eye medication

Factors	Frequency	Percentages
Had previous experience	60	55.56
Minor complaints	20	18.51
Advice from family member/friend	14	12.96
Long waiting period to access		
Health care	7	6.48
High cost of treatment	5	4.62
No reason/too busy	2	1.85
Total:	108	99.98

Table 5. Sources of self eye medication

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Patent medical stores	72	66
Visiting outreach	12	11.1
Pharmacist	10	9.2
Non- doctor eye care worker	8	7.4
Drug peddler and vendors	6	5.5
Total	108	100

DISCUSSION

The rate of self-medication in this study was 73.97%. Varying rates of ocular self-medication utilization have been reported among different populations in different parts of the world. In a hospital based study carried out in Southwest Nigeria, Ajayi et al. (2014) and Omalase et al. (2008) reported that 73.6% and 79.0% respondents respectively practiced self-medication using an array of drugs. The rate of self-medication in North Central Nigeria obtained in the present study is similar to that reported earlier in Southwest Nigeria (Ajayi et al., 2014; Omalase et al., 2008). However a lower prevalence rate of ocular self-medication of 23.3% and 59.8% from Ghana and Tanzania respectively has been reported (Kyei et al., 2014, Kagashe and Msela, 2012).

In this study, red painful eye (40%) constituted the most common indication for assessing self-eye medication followed by itching in the eye (26%). Similar findings were reported in studies which were conducted by Kadri et al.(2011) and Gupta and Malhotra (2016) where people with red eyes and those with itchy eyes respectively. Red painful eye are common in this environment and causes vary from acute conjunctivitis, corneal alceration, acute angle glaucoma, uveitis and scleritis.

In this study, antibiotics (75%) were the most common group of drugs utilized in self-medication. This finding is consistent with another study in which antibiotic use was reported in 73.9% of respondents (Anad et al., 2005). Ajayi et al.(2014) and Gupta et al.(2016) also reported that antibiotics were the commonest group of drugs used in ocular self medication among respondents in their studies. In our present study, the use of antibiotics was for mostly non-ineffective eye conditions such as painful eye, allergic conjunctivitis, refractive error and glaucoma, most of which do not require antibiotics for treatment. This situation can best described as misuse and abuse of antibiotics and have grave consequences. The emergent trend of misuse and abuse of ophthalmic drugs is a public health concern.

In our current study, the major reason for practising ocular self-medication was experience from previous ocular episode. This is contrary to the study done by Kyei et al.(2014), where the major reason was the perception that the symptoms were of a minor/simple disorder and

warranted no expert care. The patent medicine store served as the major access point for medication for the practice of ocular self medication. This is contrary to the report which was carried out by Kyei et al. (2014) and Marquez et al. (2014) where the pharmacists served as the major access point for medication.

CONCLUSION

Majority of the respondents practiced ocular self-medication. Antibiotics were the drugs mostly used while painful red eye and itching were the most common reported symptoms. Patent medicine stores were the major source of the self medicated medicine. There was a high level of inappropriate use of ocular medication because in Nigeria a wide range of prescription drugs are easily available across the counter even without a valid prescription. Public health education should be stepped up regarding the dangers of self-medication and the rational practice of ocular self-medication.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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